

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	YYQ-1-13-IG-10%RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	2	Processing Method	LRM 6 89
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2023 21:30:04 CST		
Date Processed:	10/19/2023 15:12:51 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.801	2757035	49.82	359046
2	6.199	2777182	50.18	330343

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-89-IG-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 6 89
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	9.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/14/2023 22:05:24 CST		
Date Processed:	10/19/2023 15:15:21 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.700	1220960	92.65	131433
2	6.091	96872	7.35	9342